

SIMULATING ANIMAL FUR STRUCTURE WITH SiC FIBERS AND ALUMINIUM

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ABSTRACT

A new composite plate simulating the animal fur structure has been developed using SiC fibers and aluminium. In this new composite plate SiC fibers not only be used as reinforcement but also stretch out of the aluminium matrix. The stretched fibers is about 10 mm in length and with angle of 30° to the plate. The volume fraction of the fibers in the aluminium matrix is 40 %. Every fiber of 10 μm diameter in the matrix can stretched out of the composite skin.

Heat resistant property and the air drag experiment on this composite fur specimen was tested. During the test processes no fiber was drawn out and broken.

Key words: SiC fiber, bionic design, Functionally gradient Materials, composite materials

1. INTRODUCTION

SiC fibers can be used as reinforcement to fabricate composite materials due to its high stiffness, high strength and light weight, but it have other functionally properties such as microwave absorbing and heatresistant properties [1]. To make full use of its characteristics we designed this new kind of composite — SiC (pcs) / Al simulating animal fur structure composite. The natural skin and hair structure is a fine shell to prevent the animal from rain or sun shine and to hide himself by the environment. It has been tested in the natural world for millions years.

2. FABRICATING THE FUR STRUCTURE WITH SiC FIBERS AND ALUMINIUM

The SiC fibers used here is produced from polycarbosilane by melt spinning curing and heat treatment. Its the diameter is 10 to 15 μ m. The fibers was composited with aluminium by ultrasonic liquid infiltration method. The simulated fur structure specimen is shown in Fig. 1 and 2.

Figure 1. The simulating fur specimen with SiC fibers and aluminium . $\times 2$

Figure 2. The root portion of the SiC hair. $\times 40$

In figure 1 about one third length of the SiC fibers is tidily stretched out of the composite skin and formed a fine coat of hair. Different length of the the fibers in the aluminium matrix or out of it can be easily got by changing the fabrication process. The volume fraction of the fibers in the composite skin is about 40 % .The thickness of the skin is 5 mm.

3. THE FUNCTIONALLY PROPERTIES OF THE SIMULATING FUR

3.1. Heatresistent experiment

To find the heatresistant property of the simulating fur a device was designed as figure 3. In this experiment a flame projector blasted a flame along the lines direction of the SiC hair. One thermal couple was put on the surface of the hair and the other was attached to the back side of the composite skin. A X-Y recorder was used to record the temperature change when the X-axis changed with time. The results of the test is shown on figure 4. After 350 seconds the temperatures detected by the two couples would not chagned with time and kept a temperature difference of 405 °C between the two sides of the simulating fur specimen.

Figure 3. The device for testing heatresistent property of the simulating fur specimen

Figure4. The results of heatresistent experiment.

3.2. Air Drag Experiment

A plate specimen with the sizes of $120 \times 60 \times 5$ mm was made for measuring its air dynamic property. The test was taken in wind tunnel at the wind speed of 30 M/sec.. A same sizes of aluminium plate was measured in the same conditions. The results see table 1. It shows that when the SiC hair side fronted to the wind, angle of attack is -10 Deg., the drag force would increase about 15%.

Table 1. The results of air drag experiment at the wind speed of 30 M/Sec.

Angle of attack (deg)	Drag force of the specimens (KN)	
	Simulating fur plate	Aluminium plate
10	0.0185	0.0175
0	0.0170	0.0140
-10	0.0225	0.0175

4. DISCUSSION AND SUMMARY

This simulating fur composite with SiC fibers and aluminium is like a functionally gradient materials can be used as a heat-resistant tiles for the space plane. In this simulating fur composite there is not thermor stress to break up the hair layer and the skin layer when heated or cooled. The successfully fabricating this new idea composite is a challenging to the inhomogeneous materials, it make full used of the advantages of the SiC fibers [2] .

Much of works must be done befor this simulating fur composite appllied, such as its microwave absorbing properties, mechanical properties and hot- and -cold fatigue properties. The authors would like to find cooperators over the world.

REFERENCE

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